

Spin Densities and Line-widths in ESR and Molecular Motion of Free Radicals in Solution*

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THE pioneering efforts of Sir J. C. Ghosh in the field of physical chemistry are well-known to all of us and it is hardly necessary to enumerate these. However, I feel that I must acknowledge a debt that I owe to this great pioneer in a unique way. My graduate career started in the Chemistry Department of the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore when the Department was headed by Professor S. K. Bhattacharya, a distinguished student of Sir J. C. Ghosh. Sir J. C. (as he is affectionately called) had just then left Bangalore to join as the first Director of the I.I.Ts, viz., at I.I.T., Kharagpur. Kharagpur I.I.T. has been the model for the other I.I.Ts in several respects and I.I.T. Kanpur, where I started my professional career after returning to India from Columbia University, U.S.A., has derived strength and inspiration indirectly from I.I.T., Kharagpur which bears the stamp of the genius of Sir J. C. One of our Directors at I.I.T., Kanpur, Dr. M. S. Muthana has been a close associate of Sir J. C. I therefore feel greatly moved by the honour that the Indian Chemical Society has done in choosing me as the 1972 Sir J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecturer.

1. ESR Hamiltonian and Spin Densities

The study of free radicals in solution has been tremendously aided in the past by the use of electron spin resonance (ESR) spectroscopy¹. The rich hyperfine structure (h.f.s.) in the ESR spectra of free radicals in solution can be understood in terms of the Hamiltonian.

$$H = -|\beta_e| \vec{S} \cdot g \cdot \vec{B}_0 - \frac{8\pi}{3} g_e |\beta_e| \sum_i^n g_i \beta N_i \vec{S} \cdot \vec{I}_i \delta(r_e - r_i) \quad \dots (1)$$

\vec{S} and \vec{I} refer to electron and nuclear spin.

B_0 is the static magnetic field, β_e is the Bohr magneton, β the nuclear magneton, g is the g -tensor with g_i its isotropic value. The δ -function is the Dirac delta function which refers to the probability of finding electron at the site of nucleus i . The

Hamiltonian can be written in terms of the h.f. coupling constant a_i . If $|\psi_i(0)|^2$ is the probability of finding the electron at the nucleus i then

$$a_i = \frac{8\pi}{3} g_i \beta |\psi_i(0)|^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

In the high-field limit one has then

$$H = g_e |\beta_e| S_z B_0 + g_e |\beta_e| S_z \sum_i^n a_i I_{iz} \quad \dots (3)$$

We shall be mainly concerned here with pi-electron radicals in solution with one unpaired electron per radical (2π ground state). For protons attached to sp^2 hybridized carbon in pi-electron containing aromatic free radicals we can write

$$a_H = Q\rho_\pi^c \quad \dots (4)$$

where a_H is the h.f. coupling constant for the proton attached to the carbon and ρ_π^c is the pi-orbital spin density on this carbon atom. Equation (4) is the well-known McConnell equation². A variety of modifications of the McConnell equation has been proposed and in all these equations the concept of "spin density" is used. The essential point to bear here is that we can have ρ as +1 or -1 as extreme values since it is the difference in total probability having "up" (\uparrow) and "down" (\downarrow) spins. In other words,

$$\rho = P_\uparrow - P_\downarrow \quad \dots (5)$$

If one uses ordinary (restricted) molecular orbital theory³ in the Hückel form for pi-systems it is possible to relate ρ to the coefficient C_{i_0} of the unpaired electron orbital as

$$\rho_{i^\pi} = C_{i_0}^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

ρ_{i^π} is the spin density on the i -th pi-atomic orbital (A.O.). However, the spin density obtained in this manner can have only positive values whereas both positive and negative spin densities can occur¹. The McLachlan procedure⁴ uses Hückel coefficients in a perturbation approach to obtain both positive and negative spin densities. Thus

$$\rho_r = C_{mr}^2 + \lambda \sum_s \pi_{rs} C_{ms}^2 \quad \dots (7)$$

* Based on the Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (1972) delivered in February 1973 at Calcutta.

π_{rs} is the mutual atom-atom polarisability³ and λ is an adjustable parameter. The Pariser-Parr-Pople (P.P.P.) method³ has been applied to pi-radicals in the unrestricted form. Amos and Snyder⁵ have shown that in using this approach it is essential to note that the unrestricted Hartree-Fock (UHF) approach yields a wave function which is not always an eigenfunction of the S^2 operator although it is an eigenfunction of the S_z operator. It is therefore necessary to either project out the wanted (in our case doublet) component or annihilate the undesired higher components. It was further shown that annihilation of the next higher component is sufficient. In our work⁶ we have employed this procedure and annihilated to quartet component to get better S^2 eigenvalues. The all-valence electron formalism of Pople and co-workers⁷ in the form of CNDO/2 and INDO methods can also be employed in the unrestricted form to yield spin densities. As will be discussed later in this article the all-valence electron approach yields reliable spin densities and can be employed in line-width theories to obtain molecular parameters such as rotational correlation times.

2. Some Results of Spin density calculations using Hückel and McLachlan Procedures

We shall now illustrate some of the applications of Hückel and McLachlan type approaches for the calculation of spin densities. The examples are taken from our work at Kanpur. The spin densities in 1,2,5-thiadiazole, 2,1,3-benzothiadiazole and naphtho[2,3-c]-1,2,5-thiadiazole were calculated by us⁸ using Hückel approach (eqn. 6) and it is gratifying to see the agreement with experiment⁹. Hückel and McLachlan spin density calculations were also carried out by us on azuleno [5,6,7-cd] phenalene¹⁰. Experimental confirmation of our results is not yet available. In the case of the radical anion of sym-trinitro benzene reduced by lithium metal we found¹¹ that using Hückel approach it was possible to establish that the lithium cation is bound to the oxygen atoms of a given nitro group and not shared between two nitro groups. A variation of the electronegativity parameter (h_0) was carried out in this study.

In the case of ESR spectrum of tetraphenylcyclopentadienone radical anion¹² a surprisingly narrow spread (about 5 gauss) of the spectrum with 39 lines was observed. The spectrum could be interpreted very satisfactorily on the basis of the four phenyl groups being twisted out of plane from the plane of the five-membered ring. An angle of twist of 30° gave excellent agreement with the experimental spectrum. This twist is clearly due to the steric repulsion between the phenyl rings in the five-membered ring and reduces the delocalization of the unpaired electron on to the phenyl rings. The unpaired electron essentially remains confined to the five-membered ring. This interesting result on the geometry of the radical has been made available, thanks to ESR spectroscopy and theoretical study of spin densities. We shall deal with the McLachlan spin density results obtained by us in the case of

radical anions of 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl and 1,8 dinitronaphthalene as well as nitrobenzotriles when we discuss the line-width results.

3. Spin Exchange Rates in Free Radicals in Solution

ESR studies can, under suitable conditions, yield information on intramolecular electron exchange rates¹³⁻¹⁷. In our study on the 2,2'-dinitrodiphenyl ether and sulfide radical anions¹⁸ we found that by preparing these radicals by alkali metal reduction in tetrahydrofuran (THF) as solvent the spectra showed features due to the metal ion also. By first preparing the radicals in this manner and diluting the THF with dimethyl formamide (DMF) we could eliminate metal coupling effects. Whereas the two nitro group nitrogens exhibited same coupling constant a_N in the sulfide case the two nitrogens were inequivalent in the ether case. On the other hand the protons in the corresponding positions of the two phenyl rings showed equivalence in both the cases. If we denote the situation where the electron is confined to one phenyl ring, r (case A) or the other, s (case B) then the ESR transition including h.f. interaction of nuclei in the two rings can be written as

$$\omega_A(m_\mu^r) = \omega_0 + |\gamma_e| \sum_\mu a_\mu m_\mu^r \quad \dots (8)$$

(ring r)

$$\omega_B(m_\mu^s) = \omega_0 + |\gamma_e| \sum_\mu a_\mu m_\mu^s \quad \dots (9)$$

(ring s)

m_μ^r and m_μ^s are the nuclear quantum numbers of the nucleus in ring r and its symmetrically equivalent partner in ring s , respectively. γ_e is the gyromagnetic ratio for the electron and ω the resonant frequency. If the electron exchange between the two phenyl rings is slow then we have the spectrum due to localised interaction in one ring superposed on to that from the other. This is the case for the nitrogen coupling in the ether radical. Here the two rings are equivalent and we get the expected spectrum for nitrogen inequivalence ($a_N = 9.12G$ and $a_N = 0$). The rate of exchange is however fast as far as the proton couplings are concerned. If the exchange frequency is ν_{ex} and if the hyperfine frequency is denoted by $|\gamma_e| \cdot |\Delta a_\mu|$, where Δa_μ is the variation in h.f. frequency then the "fast" electron exchange case corresponds to

$$\nu_{ex} > |\gamma_e| \cdot |\Delta a_\mu| \quad \dots (10)$$

This appears to be so for protons in both the cases. But for the nitrogen h.f. interaction in the sulfide case we find another situation. Here both the nitrogens and the protons are equivalent as far as the r and s rings are concerned. This implies that we are observing in the "fast" case an average of the frequencies due to the two rings. In other words

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\omega}(m_\mu^r, m_\mu^s) &= \frac{1}{2}[\omega_A(m_\mu^r) + \omega_B(m_\mu^s)] \\ &= \omega_0 + |\gamma_e| \sum_\mu M_\mu \bar{a}_\mu \quad \dots (11) \end{aligned}$$

with $M_\mu = m_\mu^r + m_\mu^s$ and \bar{a}_μ the average value of the h.f.s. constant over the exchange motions, (i.e., $\bar{a}_\mu = \frac{1}{2}a_\mu$ in our case). Looking at the ESR coupling data in this manner we can set a lower limit on the exchange frequency in 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl sulfide radical anion and fortunately both a lower and an upper limit in the 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl ether case. The results can be summarized as follows.

$\nu_{ex} > 32.5$ MHz—sulfide case

13.35 MHz $< \nu_{ex} < 25.5$ MHz—ether case.

It is likely that the higher exchange rate in these radicals as compared to 4,4'-dinitrobiphenyl sulfide^{15,16} is due to the favourable disposition of the nitrogroups. Our observations on 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl ether leading to both upper and lower limits for ν_{ex} appears to be the first of its kind reported in the literature.

4. Line-width Effects in the ESR Spectra of Radicals in Solution : General Features

Before we discuss the details of our analysis of line-widths it is worthwhile pointing out some general features. In a normal ESR spectrum of a free radical in solution one obtains h.f. lines which exhibit similar widths. However, in some cases one finds lines of markedly differing widths. Usually, the central part of the spectrum in such cases consists of sharp lines while the low and high field lines differ in having different widths. Sometimes lines may alternate in their widths as well: that is, a narrow line is followed by a broad line followed by a narrow line and so on. The changes in the appearance of these spectra brought about by changing the solvent or temperature are truly remarkable and rewarding to an experimenter. The analysis of such spectra can become very complicated especially in the case of overlapping lines and a computer fitting of the experimental spectra can help in the process. If alkali metal ions are employed in the generation of free radicals the line-width effects could be a result of association between the radical anion and the metal cation. In some cases h.f.s. due to metal couplings can also be seen. Electro-generation of the radicals can avoid the metal coupling effects and it is advisable as a rule to have both varieties of spectra to aid analysis. This is not to imply that electrogenerated radicals cannot exhibit line width effects. They can also show these features, of course.

The work that will be discussed here pertains to the line-width effects that we have observed¹⁹⁻²¹ in the ESR spectra of a number of nitroaromatic radical ions such as 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl, 1,8-dinitronaphthalene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzotrionitriles. Both solvent and temperature variation studies have been carried out by us. In such experimental studies extreme care must be exercised in the preparation of the radicals. Proper attention should be paid to material, especially solvent, purity, handling in the vacuum line, controlled electrolytic conditions and preferably use of polarographic and/or cyclic voltametric methods. Reproducibility of spectra can be

achieved only under these circumstances. Measurements of line-widths is another aspect of the problem. Instrumental broadening (broadening due to modulation included) can be excessive and lead to smearing out of line-width effects. Dilute solutions are therefore necessary (10^{-3} – $10^{-4}M$). Fortunately theoretical treatment relies on the differential line-width effects within the spectrum and hence relative line-widths can be employed in theoretical analysis.

5. Line-width and Density Matrix Theory

The various modulating motions in a free radical, including electron exchange, can in principle contribute to the line-widths. In the slow motion case one can essentially employ the type of approach originally employed by Gutowsky²² and co-workers for NMR, i.e., obtain the solutions of the Bloch equations. This is a phenomenological approach. However, a better insight into the processes can be obtained by following the so-called, 'relaxation matrix theory', approach of Freed and Fraenkel²³ in suitable cases. This approach has been employed by us here. The relaxation matrix approach has its origins in the original density matrix formalism of Kubo and Tomita²⁴, Wangsness and Bloch^{25,26}, Redfield²⁷, Abragam²⁸ and others^{29,30}. Earlier, Kivelson³¹ developed a theory of line-widths in ESR spectra of free radicals in solution. This theory is inadequate in explaining the observed line-widths in the ESR spectra of free radicals when there is degeneracy of nuclear spin states. The Freed-Fraenkel approach follows the Redfield-Abragam formalism and yields also an expression for the frequency shifts³². Experimental measurement of frequency shifts yield the correlation time τ_c for the motion involved. We shall summarize here the essentials of the relaxation matrix theory for purposes of the discussion.

The total Hamiltonian of the spin system can be generally written as

$$H = H_0 + H_1(t) \quad \dots (12)$$

H_0 is the time-independent zero-order Hamiltonian and $H_1(t)$ is a fluctuating time-dependent perturbation which causes relaxation and line-broadening. The Hermitian operator $H_1(t)$ is assumed to be a stationary random function³³ with a time-average value of zero. However, the mean square fluctuation of $H_1(t)$ contributes to the relaxation time. If $\alpha, \alpha', \beta, \beta'$ are the eigenstates of H_0 then the correlation function for the stationary random perturbation $H_1(t)$ is given by

$$G_{\alpha\beta\alpha'\beta'}(\tau) = H_1(t)_{\alpha\beta} H_1^*(t+\tau)_{\alpha'\beta'} \quad \dots (13)$$

where $H_1(t)_{\alpha\beta} = \langle \alpha | H_1(t) | \beta \rangle$ and * denotes the complex conjugate. The correlation function is independent of the origin of time t and depends only on the interval τ . Also it is assumed $G(\tau) = G(-\tau)$. For time τ less than some critical time τ_c called the "correlation time" the variation of $H_1(t)$ with time may be considered negligible i.e., $H_1(t) \approx H_1(t+\tau)$.

For $\tau > \tau_c$, $H_1(t+\tau)$ gets less correlated progressively and as τ is lengthened $G(\tau)$ goes to zero. In other words, $G(\tau)$ has a maximum at $\tau = 0$ and falls off for $|\tau| > \tau_c$. We define the spectral density J as

$$J_{\alpha\beta\alpha'\beta'}(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\tau) \exp(-i\omega\tau) d\tau \quad \dots (14)$$

which is the Fourier transform of the correlation function.

In line-width studies we are interested in the quantity $G_k^{(Mag)}(t)$ which refers to the correlation function for the X-component of the magnetization (M_x) corresponding to a transition k between Zeeman levels. In terms of $M_x(t)$ which is given by

$$M_x(t) = \exp[i(H_0 + H_1)t] M_x \exp - [i(H_0 + H_1)t] \quad \dots (15)$$

we have

$$G_k^{(Mag)}(t) = \text{Trace}[M_x(t)M_x] \quad \dots (16)$$

The correlation function can be obtained from the eigenvalues $\lambda_i^{(k)}$ of the relaxation matrix R with elements $R_{\alpha\alpha'\beta\beta'}$. The relaxation matrix obeys the equation²⁷

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\alpha\alpha'}}{dt} = i(\alpha' - \alpha)\sigma_{\alpha\alpha'} + \sum_{\beta\beta'} R_{\alpha\alpha'\beta\beta'} \sigma_{\beta\beta'} \quad \dots (17)$$

where σ is the density matrix.

In general the R matrix is complex.

The second term in equation 17 arises due to the perturbation term $H_1(t)$. If $H_1(t)$ modulates only energy levels α and α' without inducing any transition between them (secular perturbation) then R will be always diagonal. Even if off-diagonal elements are present in R a unitary transformation can bring the R into the diagonal form. The eigenvalues of R , viz., $\lambda_i^{(k)}$ are related to the line-width parameter T_2 as

$$T_{2,i}^{(k)} = -[\lambda_i^{(k)}]^{-1} \quad \dots (18)$$

The intensity of a line is given by

$$I_k(\omega) = \frac{D_k}{\pi} \left\{ \frac{T_{2,i}^{(k)}}{1 + [T_{2,i}^{(k)}]^2 (\omega - \omega_k)^2} \right\} \quad \dots (19)$$

D_k is the degeneracy factor. The spectrum is the sum of the lines of Lorentzian shapes of different widths and thus, in general, the shape of a composite line is not Lorentzian.

6. The Freed-Fraenkel Theory of Line-widths

In the Freed-Fraenkel approach^{23,32} one considers $H_1(t)$ as

$$H_1(t) = H_1^{(I)}(t) + H_1^{(D)}(t) + H_1^{(G)}(t) + H_1^{(Q)}(t) \quad \dots (20)$$

$H_1^{(I)}(t)$ refers to the isotropic part, $H_1^{(D)}(t)$ to the dipolar part, $H_1^{(G)}(t)$ to the g -tensor part and $H_1^{(Q)}(t)$ to the quadrupolar part of the perturbation. In what follows we neglect the quadrupolar part and consider the first three terms only. Using irreducible tensor notation^{34,35} $H_1(t)$ can be written as

$$H_1(t) = \sum_{\mu,i} F'_{\mu,i}{}^{(L,m)}(t) A'_{\mu,i}{}^{(L,-m)} \quad \dots (21)$$

where $F'_{\mu,i}{}^{(L,m)}(t)$ is a function of the spatial variables only and $A'_{\mu,i}{}^{(L,-m)}$ contains only spin operators. The subscript μ distinguishes different types of perturbations and i refers to the different nuclei in the radical. The interactions are represented by irreducible spherical tensors of rank L and component m . Isotropic perturbations have $L=0$ and anisotropic ones, have $L=2$. The correlation function can be obtained in the desired coordinate system by transforming the operators using Wigner matrices and taking their average over these matrices for taking into account molecular tumbling. Expressions for correlation functions for isotropic and anisotropic modulations can be thus obtained^{23,32}. $G(\tau)$ is then written as a sum over terms $g_{ij}(\tau)$ and $j_{ij}(\omega)$ which are again correlation functions and spectral densities involving nuclei i and j . One of the restrictions placed by the relaxation matrix theory is that the modulating motion must be rapid but not too rapid. In other words $\tau_c^2 \gamma_e^2 < (\delta a)^2 \ll 1$ and $(\omega_0 \tau_c)^2 \ll 1$. Even so a number of systems of physical interest lend themselves to a study by the relaxation matrix theory approach.

The modulations of isotropic h.f. interactions can be caused by a variety of factors like intramolecular motions and intramolecular interactions between the radical and the solvent or non-radical solutes $H_1^{(I)}(t)$ can be written as

$$H_1^{(I)}(t) = \sum_i (a_i(t) - \bar{a}_i) \vec{I}_i \cdot \vec{S} \quad \dots (22)$$

where \bar{a} is the average value of the h.f. coupling. We denote two nuclei i and j of the same species as completely equivalent if H_0 as well as $H_1(t)$ are symmetric with respect to interchange of i and j . If $\bar{a}_i = \bar{a}_j$ but $a_i(t) \neq a_j(t)$ then the nuclei i and j are equivalent but not completely equivalent with respect to perturbation $H_1(t)$. If we consider only the real part of the relaxation matrix we can obtain the line-width expression, but in order to get frequency shifts we have to consider the imaginary part as well. Considering only the real part it can be shown²³ that the correlation functions are given by

$$g_{ij}^{(I)}(\tau) = \gamma_e^2 \langle [a_i(t) - \bar{a}_i][a_j(t) - \bar{a}_j] \rangle \quad \dots (23)$$

and the spectral densities by

$$j_{ij}(\omega) = \int_0^\infty g_{ij}^{(I)}(\tau) \cos \omega\tau d\tau \quad \dots (24)$$

The secular terms in $H_1^{(I)}(t)$ give rise to $j_{ij}^{(I)}(0)$ while the non-secular terms give $j_{ij}^{(I)}(\omega)$. Since non-secular terms are smaller than the secular terms by an amount $(1 + \omega^2\tau_c^2)^{-1}$ we need consider only the secular terms when $(\omega_0\tau_c)^2 \gg 1$. With only $j_{ij}^{(I)}(0)$ terms the R matrix is diagonal. Thus we get for the general case of a free radical containing groups of inequivalent nuclei r, s etc.²³

$$T_2^{-1}(M_{ra}, M_{rb}, \dots, M_{sg}, M_{sh} \dots) \\ = \sum_{ru} \sum_{sv} j_{rusv}(0) M_{ru} M_{sv} + T^{-1}_{2,0} \quad \dots (25)$$

where $M_u = \sum_{i \text{ in } u} m_i$. $T_{2,0}^{-1}$ is the line-width from mechanisms other than isotropic modulation.

The two-site jump model is a very attractive one and we have employed it in our studies a di-nitro aromatic radical anions. For a single group of completely equivalent nuclei the line-width is given by²³

$$[T_2^{(M)}]^{-1} = j^{(I)}_{aa}(0)M^2 + T^{-1}_{2,0} \quad \dots (26)$$

since $j^{(I)}_{aa}(0) = j^{(I)}_{ab}(0)$. We refer to the situation of $j^{(I)}_{aa}(0) = j^{(I)}_{ab}(0)$ as "in-phase" correlation. For a single group of equivalent nuclei having two sub-groups of completely equivalent nuclei

$$T^{-1}_{2,0}(M_a, M_b) = j^{(I)}_{aa}(0)(M_a - M_b)^2 + T^{-1}_{2,0} \quad \dots (27)$$

where $j^{(I)}_{aa}(0) = -j^{(I)}_{ab}(0) = \gamma_e^2\tau_c < (\delta a)^2 >$. It must be pointed out here that if a_I and a_{II} are the two h.f. coupling constants then $\bar{a} = \frac{1}{2}(a_I + a_{II})$ and $<(\delta a)^2 > = \frac{1}{4}(a_I - a_{II})^2$. We refer to the situation $j^{(I)}_{aa}(0) = -j^{(I)}_{ab}(0)$ as "out of phase" correlation. The 'in-phase' correlation is a consequence of the nuclei being completely equivalent while the "out-of-phase" correlation leads to the familiar alternating line-width phenomenon. Appreciable dynamic frequency shifts are associated with isotropic interactions. Anisotropic modulations are unimportant in this regard. The experimentally measured frequency shifts for a spectrum exhibiting alternating line-width effects can be useful in determining spectral densities and τ_c values since we have $j^{(I)}_{aa}(0) = -j^{(I)}_{ab}(0)$.

We have so far discussed the $H^{(I)}_1(t)$ term in equation (20). $H^{(D)}_1(t)$ and $H^{(G)}_1(t)$ give rise to the anisotropic contributions to the line-widths. We make use of the correlation time τ_R and $j^{(G)}$, the spectral density to get²³

$$[T^{-1}_{2,0}]^{(G)} = \frac{8}{3}j^{(G)}(0)B_0^2 \quad \dots (28)$$

$j^{(G)}$ is a function of τ_R and the components of the g -tensor. The spectral densities for the dipolar interaction can be written as^{23,36}

$$j^{(D)}_{ij} = j^{(D)}_{ij}(0) = \frac{4}{5}\pi^2\zeta_i\zeta_j\tau_R \sum_{m=-2}^2 D_i^{(m)}D_i^{(-m)} \quad \dots (29)$$

where

$$\zeta_i = \frac{1}{2}\pi|\gamma_e|\gamma_i\hbar \quad \dots (30)$$

γ_i is the magnetogyric ratio for the nucleus i . The D 's are dipolar coefficients defined as

$$D_i^{(m)} = \left(\frac{6\pi}{5}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \langle \psi | r_i^{-3} i_{2m}(\theta', \phi') | \psi \rangle \quad \dots (31)$$

$i_{2m}(\theta', \phi')$ are spherical harmonics of order two and the prime indicates molecule-fixed axes.

There are also cross-terms between the dipolar and g -tensor interactions and the spectral densities are given by

$$j_i^{(DG_2)} = j_i^{(DG_2)}(0) = \left(\frac{\pi\beta_e}{5\hbar}\right) \zeta_i\tau_R \sum_{m=-2}^2 D_i^{(m)}g_i^{(-m)} \quad \dots (32)$$

$g_i^{(m)}$'s are the spherical g -tensor components in the irreducible representation. They can be expressed in terms of the principal components of the g -tensor along the molecule-fixed axes. The complete expression for the line-width contribution due to the dipolar terms leads to a theoretically expected line-width variation of the following form

$$\Delta(\tilde{M}_i, \tilde{M}_j \dots) = A + \sum_i B_i \tilde{M}_i + \sum_i C_i \tilde{M}_i^2 + \sum_{i \neq j} E_{ij} \tilde{M}_i \tilde{M}_j \quad \dots (33)$$

\tilde{M}_i refers to the spectral index number for nucleus i or group i of completely equivalent nuclei. The spectral index is taken as positive on the high field side. The coefficients C_i , E_{ij} and B_i yield the spectral densities $j^{(D)}_{ii}(\omega)$, $j^{(D)}_{ij}(\omega)$ and $j^{(DG_2)}_{ij}(\omega)$ respectively²³. The ratio of the spectral densities $j^{(D)}_{ij}(\omega)$ to the rotational correlation time τ_R can be obtained in terms of the dipolar coefficients (equation 31) which can be evaluated from a knowledge of the spin density (ρ) distribution (vide Section 1) and the molecular geometry of the radical. Hence τ_R can be estimated using any one of the spectral densities $j^{(D)}_{ij}(\omega)$ obtained from experimental line-width data. One can also calculate other spectral densities from the values of τ_R thus obtained as well as the dipolar coefficients and thus obtain better check on the agreement. The quadratic term containing $\tilde{M}_i \tilde{M}_j$ in equation (33), where i and j are inequivalent nuclei, is useful in determining the relative signs of \bar{a}_i and \bar{a}_j . In the next section we illustrate the applications of the Freed-Fraenkel theory to a few systems.

7. Some Results of the Application of Relaxation Matrix Theory to Free Radicals in Solution

The anion radical of 2,2'-dinitrobiphenyl has been prepared by reduction with lithium, sodium and potassium in dimethoxy ethane (DME) and THF.

ESR spectra of dilute solutions of these radicals were studied¹⁹ in the temperature range $+50^\circ$ to -80° . The two nitrogen couplings are not equivalent in the anion radical obtained by lithium reduction while they are equal in the case of sodium and potassium reduction in both DME and THF. Anomalous line-width behaviour was observed in all these spectra depending on temperature and solvent as well as the cation. The spectra were examined in the light of the Freed-Fraenkel theory using the two-site jump model for the metal ion association to the nitro group. The scheme is represented as below :

(X = metal).

The observed dependence of the line-widths on m^2 could be satisfactorily explained on the basis of out-of-phase correlation and isotropic modulation. The data also yielded quantitative results on the spectral densities and thus on the relative cation solvation by different solvents. The larger h.f. coupling constant was ascribed to the nitrogen site where the cation is complexed. It was thought at that time¹⁹ that the observed line-width variations could be due to the favourable spatial disposition of the two nitro groups in the radical anion of 2,2'-dinitro biphenyl and hence other systems such as 1,8-dinitronaphthalene should also exhibit similar effects. This prediction was indeed verified in our later study²⁰. ESR spectra of radical anions of 2,2'-dinitro biphenyl and 1,8-dinitronaphthalene generated electrolytically were examined²⁰. Anhydrous DMF was used and the temperature range was 20° to -80° . The spectra indeed showed line-width effects and dynamic frequency shifts could be also measured experimentally. The two-site jump model along with the Freed-Fraenkel theory enabled us to compute the spectral densities for both isotropic and anisotropic intramolecular interactions. In conjunction with the experimental dynamic frequency shifts, the spectral densities yielded the correlation times for modulations of isotropic splittings. Out-of-phase correlation of nitrogen splittings of the two nitro groups could explain the observed trends in spin densities satisfactorily. We next investigated the details of the modulating motions using spin densities as our guide. McLachlan and UHF spin densities after annihilation of the quartet component (UHFAA) were calculated for different geometries. An investigation into the question of appropriate sigma-pi parameters for ^{14}N splittings was also carried out²⁷. Satisfactory agreement was obtained between experimental and calculated h.f. splitting constants when the two planes of the phenyl rings of 2,2'-dinitro

biphenyl are twisted 40° from the trans-planer configuration with respect to the nitro groups. This result is reminiscent of the earlier results on tetraphenyl cyclopentadienone radical anion (vide Section 2). In order to explain the out-of-phase correlation and the observed couplings, it has been suggested²⁰ that the modulating motions are such that when one of the nitro groups is in the plane of the ring, the other one is out-of-plane. A similar model also explains the results in the case of 1,8-dinitronaphthalene radical anion. The relative motion of the two nitro groups has been described as a "see-saw" motion.

In our study of the line-width effects in the ESR spectra of electrogenerated radical anions of nitrobenzonitriles we examined²¹ the ESR spectra of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzonitriles in DMF over the temperature range 20° to -70° . Improved resolution was obtained in the case of *m*-nitrobenzonitrile radical anion. From a consideration of the experimental coupling constants and calculated spin densities the nitro group was inferred to be coplaner with the phenyl ring in the case of *o*-nitrobenzonitrile. The Freed-Fraenkel theory was again employed for the analysis of the line-width data and using the dipolar coefficients (equation 31) calculated from McLachlan, UHFAA and IWDO spin densities correlation times for molecular tumbling motions were obtained for *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzonitrile radical anions. The INDO spin densities appear to be more reliable and τ_R values lie in the 10^{-10} secs. range. Our line-width analysis also led to the determination of the signs of a few proton and nitrogen h.f. coupling constants. We have carried out similar investigations on the nitrobenzonitriles using alkali metal-reduced radicals also²⁸.

3. Conclusion

We have seen how the study of spin densities and line-widths in conjunction with the relaxation matrix approach can yield valuable information on molecular structure and motion of free radicals in solution. The examples presented here point to further useful applications along these lines. Ion solvation, electron exchange, ion-ion association, correlation times, models for molecular motion, signs of h.f. coupling constants are just some of the many topics that can be effectively studied in this manner.

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